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ANALYZING THE NEED FOR TOURISM LOGISTICS DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: Past few decades the tourism system of Uzbekistan has developed rapidly and also its impact in economy increased significantly. In order to continue this development we need pay attention to logistics system, its development and optimization. This thesis is aimed to analyzing current position of tourism logistics system in Uzbekistan, to identify factors which are destroying for development of tourism logistics and to clarify the need for development of logistics infrastructure.

The introduction part consists of 2 main research questions with full answers. The first research question is about the main key factors in the development of tourism logistics and its impact to tourism industry and local economy. This part includes clear information about factors and how they impact to economy with examples.

The location of Uzbekistan is convenient not only geographically but also with climatic condition for tourism. Moreover many big transport roads of Central Asia are located as well as there are a lot of historical and cultural monuments, attractive nature and touristic resource in Uzbekistan. But there are some problems like old transports system, lack of hotels with high standards, poor service system, high cost of transport, poor developed transit and logistics system and other legal and bureaucratic obstacles are decreasing effectiveness of tourism system. In second chapter of thesis we analyze main problems of tourism logistics, impact of tourism logistics in local economy, contacts of hotels with other service sectors and transportation system. Apart from this, according to international experiences, other authors' research works we will see method of improving tourism logistics and its branches as to optimize transport directions, to facilitate accessing to touristic places, to give some advices for improving hotels and service sectors. Moreover in that chapter author compares some authors' research work with each other and gives personal view.

In methodology part author describes which kind of methods author used for collecting data and how created questions for survey.

In result and discussion part author analyzes personal survey. Apart from this, it includes analyze of answers, data and statistics, identified problems in tourism logistics according others answers.

In the last part, the goal is to generalize all the data and provide my own opinion based on the survey and research.

Key words: UNESCO, transport infrastructure, accommodations, railways, airways, public transports, digital technology, local branding, GDP, local economy, international investment, tourism industry.

Annotatsiya: So'ngi yillarda O'zbekiston turizm tarmog'i jadallik bilan rivojlanib kelyapti va uning iqtisodiyotga qo'shgan ta'siri ham similarly darajada. Rivojlanishni shu zayilda davom ettirish uchun esa turizm logistikasining rivojlanishiga va uni optimallashtirishga ko'proq e'tibor qaratish lozim. Ilmiy ishning asosiy maqsadi ham O'zbekiston turizm logistikasining hozirgi holatini tahlil qilish, bu sohani rivojlantirishda to'siq bo'layotgan omillarni aniqlash va bu sohani rivojlantirish zaruriyatini aniqlashdir.

Ilmiy ishning kirish bo'limi 3 ta asosiy qismdan tashkil topgan. Birinchi qismda turizm logistikasining rivojiga ta'sir etuvchi omillar and turizm logistikasing iqtisodiyotga va turizm industriyasiga ta'siri aniq misollar bilan o'rganiladi.

O'zbekistonning geografik joylashuvi va iqlimi ham tursim uchun juda qulay hisoblanadi. Bundan tashqari O'rta Osiyoning eng katta transit yo'llari ham O'zbekistonda joylashgan bo'lib, ko'pgina tarixiy va madaniy obidalar, go'zal tabiat hamda ko'pgina sayyohlik manbalarini ham o'z ichiga oladi. Biroq bu sohadagi ba'zi muammolar ya'ni eski ttransport tizimi, yuqori darajadagi mehmonxonalarning kamligi, xizmatlar sifatining pastligi, transportlarning qimmatligi va boshqa shu kabi muammolar turizm samaradorligini pasayishiga olib kelmoqda. Ilmiy ishning ikkinchi bo'limida shu kabi muammolar tahlil qilingan, turizm logistikasining iqtisodiyotga ta'siri o'rganiladi. Bundan tashqari, bu bo'lim xalqaro tajribalar va boshqa mualliflar fikrlariga asosan turizm logistikasining rivojlantirish yo'llari, transport tizimini takomillashtirish usullari, mehmonxonalar va xizmatlarni samarali tashkil qilish strategiyalarini o'z ichiga oladi. Shu bilan bir qatorda, bu bo'limda ba'zi mualliflarning fikrlari o'zaro taqqoslanadi va muallif o'z shaxsiy fikrini ham bildiradi.

Metodologiya bo'limida muallif qaysi metodlardan foydalanganligi ma'lumot yig'ish uchun va so'rovnoma savollarini qanday tuzganligi haqida to'liq ma'lumot beriladi.

Natija va tahlil bo'limida muallifning so'rovnomasi tahlil qilinadi. Bundan tashqari javoblar birma bir tahlil qilingan, ulardan ma'lumot va faktlar olinadi va javoblar orqali turizm sohasidagi muammolar aniqlanadi.

Oxirgi xulosa qismida barcha to'plangan ma'lumotlar umumiyashtirilgan holda muallifning shaxsiy fikri yoritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: UNESCO, transport infratuzilmasi, turar joy, temiryo'l, havo yo'li, jamoat transportlari, raqamli texnologiya, mahalliy brend, YIM, mahalliy iqtisodiyot, xalqaro investitsiya, turizm industriyasi.

Аннотация: В последние годы туристическая индустрия Узбекистана стремительно развивается, и её влияние на экономику также существенно. Для продолжения этого развития необходимо уделять больше внимания развитию и оптимизации туристической логистики. Основная цель научной работы — анализ текущего состояния туристической логистики в Узбекистане, выявление факторов, препятствующих развитию этой отрасли, и определение необходимости её развития.

Вводная часть научной работы состоит из 3 основных частей. В первой части исследуются факторы, влияющие на развитие туристической логистики, и её влияние на экономику и туристическую отрасль на конкретных примерах. Географическое положение и климат Узбекистана также весьма благоприятны для туризма. Кроме того, через Узбекистан проходят крупнейшие транзитные пути Центральной Азии, что включает в себя множество исторических и культурных памятников, прекрасную природу и многочисленные туристические ресурсы. Однако некоторые проблемы в этой сфере, а именно устаревшая транспортная система, нехватка высококлассных отелей, низкое качество услуг, высокая стоимость транспорта и другие подобные проблемы, приводят к снижению эффективности туризма. Во втором разделе научной работы анализируются такие проблемы, изучается влияние туристической логистики на экономику. Кроме того, в этом разделе, основанном на международном опыте и мнении других авторов, рассматриваются пути развития туристической логистики, методы совершенствования транспортной системы, стратегии эффективной организации гостиничного бизнеса и услуг. В то же время, в этом разделе сравниваются мнения некоторых авторов, а также высказывается личное мнение автора.

В разделе «Методология» представлена полная информация о методах, использованных автором для сбора информации, и о том, как он формулировал вопросы анкеты.

В разделе «Результаты и анализ» анализируется анкета автора. Кроме того, ответы анализируются по отдельности, из них извлекается информация и факты, и на основе ответов выявляются проблемы в сфере туризма.

В заключительном заключении обобщаются все собранные данные и излагается личное мнение автора.

Ключевые слова: ЮНЕСКО, транспортная инфраструктура, жилье, железная дорога, воздух, общественный транспорт, цифровые технологии, локальный бренд, ВВП, местная экономика, международные инвестиции, туристическая индустрия.

INTRODUCTION

The tourism industry is being one of the most important parts of economy during the last years. As the tourism industry is very comprehensive and includes many spheres like transportation, hotel business, services, manufacturing and logistics. The development of logistics will help for improving economy, creating new job opportunities, exchanging cultures and strengthening international relationship. Therefore developing tourism logistics is the most important process for economic and social status of the country. The aim of research is analyzing the importance development of tourism logistics, its impact to the ecologic, social and economic sides of Uzbekistan.

The main reasons of developing tourism logistics are organizing different touristic services efficiency and in high level, using various and modern approaches for attracting visitors. In order to do these processes,

developing transport infrastructure and directing it for touristic purposes, interconnecting all branches of logistics and doing modernization, improving the quality of services, using modern technologies are being the most important factors. The development of tourism logistics creates an opportunity to increase global competitiveness of Uzbekistan and gain strong place on international tourism maps. Because of this, in the country the through creating big international airways, transport centers and touristic areas, increasing branches of hotels, improving tourism infrastructure, servicing in a high standards is waiting in the near future.

The key factors in the development of tourism logistics of Uzbekistan and their impact to local economy and tourism industry.

These days developing tourism logistics is being one of the main tasks for Uzbekistan. As with developing tourism logistics, we can improve not only tourism industry, but also country's economic and social status, to introduce the world like a famous tourism country. The development of tourism logistics depend on some main factors. In this thesis author clarify these factors and their impact to the local economy and tourism industry (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The main factors in tourism logistics of Uzbekistan

Source: Own elaboration

The transport infrastructure. Uzbekistan is one of the famous country which has different and big tourism potential. There are a lot of ancient cities like Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva, Termiz, which is main reason to make Uzbekistan well-known to the world as touristic country. Apart from this, the natural resource of Uzbekistan, for example Chimgan Mountains, Aydar-Arnasoy lakes and Muynak city are also increase tourists' interest. The high level of tourism potential requires well developed tourism logistics. Well developed tourism logistics includes modern transport infrastructure, comfortable and safety service. It means, developed transport branches for example railways, airways and bus roads will be convenient for tourists as well as help them to achieve touristic destination faster. The development of transportation service, coming new airways companies to Uzbekistan and modernization of old airport increase the number of tourists. For example, in 2018 the local airport of Samarkand converted into international airport and as a result of it coming to 2020 the number of tourists increased up to 30-40%. Many touristic countries as Turkey, Egypt and Dubai increased the number of tourists from 20% to 40% through developing transport system. If Uzbekistan pay attention to its transport infrastructure like these countries, it will be possible to increase these numbers from 30% to 50%. The increasing the number of tourists will bring benefit to local economy as well. According to forecasts, if the number of tourists increases by 30%, the benefit to local economy namely Gross domestic product (GDP) could increase from 5% to 10%.

Hotel infrastructures and services Hotels and services is the second important factor after transportation in tourism industry. Because of this reason, these days Uzbekistan pays attention a lot to reconstructing old hotels, building facilitated and modern hotels, attracting many big investors from the world to this sphere. As a clear example of these actions we can show the meeting of the President of the Republic Uzbekistan with entrepreneurs in December 2024. In that meeting the President emphasized about improving hotel infrastructures. Moreover, it is informed that more than 20 international hotel brands will to Uzbekistan, 24 thousand bed hotel will be converted to 30 thousand bed hotel in 2025. The increasing numbers of modern hotels, touristic centers, restaurants, shopping malls enhance tourist interest and their numbers. As a result of it will be organized many new job places, the level of unemployment will decrease and country's not only economic but also social status will get better.

International relationship and investments. The creating new international partnership and attracting new investments to the development of tourism logistics is another important factor in tourism industry. The increasing touristic potential of Uzbekistan and to familiarize it to the World Market, to increase competitiveness in the

tourism industry of the World depends on to this factor. The partnership with international tourism agencies, airway companies and investors give a chance of developing tourism logistics as well as local economy.

Generally in 2024 Uzbekistan developed a lot of international partnerships with many countries. For example, Uzbekistan in the meeting with the head of Shanghai Cooperation Organization (ShCO) Shjan Min signed agreement for partnership with Kazakhstan and Belarus in tourism industry. Apart from this Uzbekistan did partnership with Explore Worldwide Company for attracting more than thousand tourists from Great Britain in 2024.

In 2024 Uzbekistan did a lot of partnership also with international airway companies and the number of flights significantly increased after this partnership. For example, from 1st December organized daily flight "Jeddah-Tashkent-Jeddah", from 14th March organized 4 times per week flight "Warsaw-Tashkent-Warsaw" and from 30th May organized charter flight twice a month "Madrid-Urgench-Madrid". Not only this but also, in 2024 modern "Airbus A321neo" airplane brought to Samarkand International Airport. All these relationship helped to develop tourism logistics and expansion of local economy. As comparing with 2023 in 2024 the number of tourists came to the Uzbekistan increased to 20,1%.

Digital technology. The role of digital technology in the development of tourism logistics is crucial. Digital technology, especially online system and mobile apps have a lot of advantages for tourists. Because of this, Uzbekistan also did a lot of development in this sphere in order to create a lot of facilities for tourists. For instance, "Visit Uzbekistan" mobile app which is very useful for tourists, give information about country, cities, historical and touristic places, hotels and restaurants as well. Another good example is in digital payment system. In order to create convenience for tourists from 2021 Uzbekistan started using international credit cards like "Visa" and "Mastercard". It makes payment process fast and easy. Buying different kind of services, booking hotels, ordering excursion through online system is easier than traditional method and also it increase efficiency of tourism logistics. Digital technology brings a lot of benefit to the tourism industry and local economy. The implantation of electron visa, mobile payment system and digital excursion make organizing travels easy and increase the number of tourists. Touristic services, for example online tourism agencies which is carried out through digital technology give chance making small business and also introduce local services to the global markets.

Ecologic stability. Ecological sides of tourism logistics and ecologic stability have a big impact in the development of tourism industry and local economy. The creating new strategies in order to develop eco tourism and to save natural resources are one of the main tasks for Uzbekistan these days. The using eco-friendly transports and technology which save energy, protecting nature help to improve tourism industry. The development sustainable tourism and eco tourism will attract new tourists and create new source of income to the local economy. Moreover, the development of eco tourism calls local people for being economical active and help creating new jobs.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The cultural and historical heritage of Uzbekistan

Nowadays Uzbekistan is becoming country which has a big tourism potential in the world. According Bozarov research work the main reason of tourists' coming to Uzbekistan is 9,608 cultural facilities, as well as 8,200 historical places of Uzbekistan and 200 of them added to the UNESCO World Heritage List. The author strongly proved his idea that it is a good opportunity to increasing tourism potential with that factor. He also estimated that many of these historical places located in Samarkand, Bukhara, Shakhrisabz, Khiva, Kokand and Termiz. But there are a lot of touristic destinations in other regions which are underestimating by tourists because of some problems (Shukurov, 2024). These facilities and places play important role for attracting tourists as Alexandra Kim also highlighted in his article that many tourists pay attention countries historical places and culture when they choose touristic destinations. According Table 2.1 it is clear that, touristic destinations, historical places are important for developing tourism industry like many authors estimated. During his research work he collected a lot of interesting data like more than 52% of tourists before visiting to Uzbekistan were in neutral position, but after visiting more than 90% of tourists were satisfied from travel and more than 88% of tourists wanted to visit again to Uzbekistan because of historical destinations and rich cultures. The author made addition to this idea that a lot of historical and cultural heritage, different traditions, colorful customs and unrepeatable cuisine will attract cultural, religious, archeological and other group of tourists. Moreover, it is known from the history Uzbekistan was the center of many ancient religious like Islam, Buddhism and Christianity and there are a lot places related to these religious. It means it is a chance of improving tourism of pilgrim and a lot of tourists. The author provided all data according his survey with open-minded questions after analyzing answers (Aleksandra, 2013).

The development of tourism industry and tourism logistics

In his article Kucharov highlighted about the development of tourism industry in recent years in Uzbekistan. The author mentioned about what kind of development is being in current years and the role of tourism organizations like tour operators, touristic centers and hotels in this development. There are 1,650 touristic centers, 989 tour operators and 869 hotels are operating in tourism sphere in Uzbekistan in order to lift up the level of tourism in a high. The author also highlighted the crucial role of airports during the development of tourism logistics. The author supported his idea with real example like there are 11 modern and facilitated airports which were become international harbors and include regular flights more than 40 countries in Uzbekistan. Moreover the author informed about the tourism infrastructure, it is the construction of the Lotto City Hotel Tashkent Palace and Hyatt Regency which is famous hotel brands in Tashkent which are being other main factors for attracting tourists (A. Kucharov, Kh. Ochilova, 2019). Despite of these developments Uzbekistan is using only 5-8% of its touristic facilities and places for touristic purpose (Aleksandra, 2013) mentioned about this in his research work. It means Uzbekistan cannot using own touristic potential fully. As a result of it, the increasing percentage of tourist is low and the process of the development tourism logistics is slow. In order to solve this kind of problems Uzbekistan is accepting many rules and normative documents and creating new strategies, Bozarov also mentioned about these strategies in his article. In order to increase the development tourism industry and its branches like touristic centers, tour operators, transportation, and accommodation and tourism logistics in 28th may 2020 accepted the Presidential Decree No2002 which was included a lot benefits for entrepreneurs. According this normative document the income tax of touristic centers and tour operators decreased. Not only this but also, they were released from land property tax (Bozarov, 2021). The author Kucharov made addition to this idea with a good real example in his research paper. The author mentioned about how Uzbekistan simplified international tourism system. From 2018 for the population of Israel, Indonesia, The Republic of Korea, Malaysia, Singapore, Turkey, Japan, Tajikistan and France visa-free regime was established. Apart from these, for the population of 39 countries the visa system was simplified (A. Kucharov, Kh. Ochilova, 2019). Definitely these developments help to improve tourism industry and tourism logistics but they are not enough develop these spheres fully like (E.N. Klochko, et al., 2016) mentioned, especially for the development of tourism logistics which is the important part of tourism industries. As tourism logistics is very complicated and includes a lot of branches. For example, transport infrastructure, accommodation, attractions, amenities and different kind of services. They are other important sides of the development process and have a big role for the process. Among all these branches (N.Arabov, et al., 2024) highlighted transportation system a lot. As well developed transportation system, airways, railways and high roads may be cause for not only increasing the number of tourists or visit again but also for their safe and comfortable travel, reaching easily to touristic destinations. But, Asadov mentioned in his article the other benefits of developing transportation system. They are traveling to the new touristic destination, saving time, increasing the number of family trips and international mobility in tourism (F.SH. Asadov, N.B. Aminova). Even though they mentioned different benefits of developing transportation, all benefits depend on the development of transportation system.

The benefits of developing tourism logistics in Uzbekistan.

One of the most important task of tourism logistics is organizing safety and unforgettable tour for tourists. This kind of tour includes easily reaching to touristic destinations, high quality food, comfortable accommodation and other these kinds of services. If the logistic system of a country is organized effectively and comfortably, it will increase tourists' satisfaction, the country's tourism potential and also its competitiveness. Apart from these there are a lot of benefits of the development of tourism logistics and the author (Na Sha, Robert Cekuta, 2019) highlighted these advantages in her research work. By developing tourism logistics the chance of bringing benefit to the local economy of the country is high. Not only this, but also it helps to improve social status of the country, living standards, to organize new business, entrepreneurship and to reduce the number of unemployed people. The author also estimated about skilled masters, who are continuing traditional handcraft in Uzbekistan and highlighted them as example one of the main factor to creating new business and developing the local entrepreneurs. The Uzbek handcrafts surprise tourists by their unrepeatabe handmade work and the demand to their work is always high according the world. As they character traditions, history, culture and ethnic origin of Uzbekistan in their work. Therefore their products are always interesting to customers or tourists and it is a good reason to create traditional brand, to find own place in the World Market. In order not to lose this position Uzbekistan should pay attention to this sphere and develop it. Uzbekistan with introducing its unrepeatabe local products will benefit not only to the local economy but also it is a good chance to improve business sphere, to provide with work the local people, to reduce the degree of losing national traditions

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research is about “Analazing the need for Tourism logistics development in Uzbekistan” and it focused on analyzing practical and theoretical aspects of tourism logistics of Uzbekistan, identifying their dependence with tourism industry, local economy, finding common problems in this sphere, cause of problems and finding their solutions. The basis of methodological consists of comprehensive and statistical analysis, systems approach, comparative evaluation, empirical methods. Each of these methods has own role during research process. In this research author used mixed methods research. The mixed methods research includes survey, secondary data analysis and interview methods. In survey method author made questionnaire about topic and participants answered these questions, the author collected data, gave ideas and suggestions according these answers. This method helped to collect additional information about the topic especially to identifying common problems which are disturbing tourists during their visit, therefore the author choose participants for answering survey mainly from other country who have been in Uzbekistan before like tourists and also gave answers from local tourists. In secondary data analysis methods the author used other researchers' data about this topic, compared them with each other, made addition and expressed own opinion. In this method the author used a lot of professors' like A.Kucharov, Aleksandra Kim, E.Bozarov, N.Arabov, E.N.Klochko, B.Safarov work for collecting secondary data and analyzed them. This method is very effective way for improving research work as it is easier than other methods. The author found information during reading books and articles related to the topic, made notes and collect them in the literature review part. After that, the author analyzed, compared data and added own opinions, suggestions to this part. The interview method helped to talk tourists face to face, gave to answers for specific questions. This method is very useful for giving a new idea but the author should choose a right people who can answer and good at this sphere especially, if this interview about scientific theme and for specific research . Therefore it a little bit difficult method as every time finding people who can answer to specific questions is not easy, sometimes specialists do not want to do an interview or some problems with time. In the figure 3.1 the author described all methods which are used in this thesis.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Making survey is one of the effective method for collecting data, giving new ideas and suggestions and identifying common problems about the topic. Therefore the author made survey in order to give more information according to answers of participants. There are 5 parts and 14 questions in the survey. Generally, 26 participants attended to this survey and many of them are foreign tourists. In order to identify their nationality and personality Part 1 is about personal details. According to answers, it is clear that only 7.7% of participants are under the 18 years, 26,9% of participants are among 18-24 years, 26,9% are among 25-34years, 15,4% are 35-44 years, 19,2% are 45-54 and only 3,8% are upper 55 years old. Part 2 is about transportation, infrastructure, roads, air lines, railways and tourism logistics. In this part the author used multiple choice questions in order to give clear answers. The first questions is identifying about level of ease to travel between main touristic destinations of Uzbekistan like Samarkand, Bukhara and Khiva. According to answers of participants, it is clear that 40% of tourists give positive opinion about this, 32% of participants in neutral position about this, 12% of tourists think it is very easy to travel between these cities and 12% of participants think it is difficult. Generally, the result of this question is good and many tourists in positive opinion about travelling along Uzbekistan.

According the result of survey it is clear that, 40% of participants used train during their travel in Uzbekistan. It means the railways of Uzbekistan more developed and common than other type of transports. The train lines are available for reaching many touristic destinations, it is fast and cheap, therefore it convenient for many tourists. But, there is a big problem with direct railway lines to many destinations. After train, the second common type of transport is bus. 28% of tourists used buses during their trip in Uzbekistan. The main reason of this is, buses are cheap, convenient for traveling with group and can easily change lines and destinations. But travel by bus take a lot of time because of slowness. The 16% of tourists prefer to use private cars or taxi for their trip. This type of transport is cheap, available every time, faster than bus and very convenient for individual tourists. The other 16% of participants used airlines for traveling within Uzbekistan. From my point view, it is low percentage for touristic country and it means we should develop our airlines and airports system.

Part 4 was open-minded questions which participants gave their suggestions and solutions in the answers. The first question was about giving personal recommendation for improving transportation and logistics services in Uzbekistan. It was one of the useful question for taking new idea as tourists can compare the logistics system of Uzbekistan with their countries' logistics system and describe differences, mistakes and similarities. According participants answers (see Appendix 3) it was known that main problems of Uzbekistan in tourism logistics are high roads, transport infrastructure, local and public transport system. According answers I got many interesting new ideas like launching a tourist transportation pass or card to simplifying moving around cities. It will be

very useful for upcoming tourists to travel. Apart from this participants suggested to making public transport comfortable with air conditioned, online booking options and clear scheduled especially buses travel around country. Improving public transportation system, for example adding international signs in the buss, making English announcement, clarifying the schedule of buses, creating useful mobile application which include all information and details about public transports, maps, lines and schedules. Fixing price of taxis or improving taxis services special for tourists or creating VIP taxis cards for tourists. The other idea was about increasing the number of direct international connections, flights and trains in order to simplify movement process.

According the result of this question, I identified that main problems which are disturb many tourists during their travel in Uzbekistan are poor transport infrastructure, lack of language barriers, mobile applications, online maps, comfortable public transports, buses and taxis.

Another open-minded question was about sustainable tourism logistics. Even though it is one of the global problem and interesting topic these days, I got some interesting idea for my research work according participants answers. Many participants supported to developing sustainable tourism logistics in Uzbekistan because of air pollution, a lot of waste and climate changes. Many participants think developing tourism logistics help to increase the number of tourists especially eco-conscious tourists, to develop eco-friendly system, to save nature and air condition. I definitely agree to this point, as these days the number of people who support eco-friendly system is increasing; therefore it is the good method for attracting many tourists with sustainable tourism logistics. Sustainable tourism logistics also help to create long term economic and environmental benefits.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

To conclude, tourism has emerged as a key focus of state policy in Uzbekistan. Although the nation possesses extensive historical, cultural, and natural resources, these prospects are not being maximized. A primary reason for this is the inadequate development of tourism logistics. This research has examined the tourism infrastructure, transportation systems, digital services, safety measures, environmental sustainability, and management frameworks throughout Uzbekistan's regions, emphasizing the main challenges and developmental requirements. The study pinpointed multiple key problems: a vague tourism logistics management framework, regional inequalities, inadequate public transport for tourists, poor signage and information availability, and airports and train stations failing to align with contemporary standards. Results clearly indicate that Uzbekistan's tourism potential is shaped not only by its abundant historical legacy but also by its capacity to showcase that legacy efficiently, safely, and conveniently through a strong logistics network. In this context, tourism logistics serves a strategic function as an integrated system for overseeing tourist movement, transit, lodging, and information access. It is essential to enlarge bus, electric bus, and train routes linking major tourist attractions in each area. Contemporary navigation and signage systems ought to be implemented in global airports, railway stations, and on highways. Urban and intercity public transit ought to incorporate digital payment systems and mobile apps along with services designed for tourists, featuring signs in English. Interactive maps, QR-code guides, and virtual tour services ought to be implemented in all key tourist areas. Key destinations should establish free Wi-Fi zones, and mobile applications must offer real-time updates on transportation, routes, and lodging options. A digital tourism logistics platform at the national level needs to be established, providing services such as hotel reservations, itinerary planning, transportation integration, and online payment options. A digital management and monitoring system in real-time must be established to observe tourist movements and offer instant guidance or help when they need. Guaranteeing Ecological Sustainability Promoting and expanding eco-friendly transportation options like electric buses, bicycles, and walking paths is essential. Regulatory guidelines need to be established to promote "green logistics" among service providers, especially in the hotel and transport industries. Please provide the text you would like me to paraphrase. Enhancing Human Resources Programs for education and training in transport management, logistics technologies, and tourism services need to be broadened at both higher education and vocational levels. To enhance service quality, regular professional development programs for transportation staff, tour guides, and hotel employees should be implemented. Improving security and ease all significant tourist locations must include medical assistance stations, police checkpoints, and emergency communication centers. Mobile apps must provide immediate access to emergency services, such as healthcare, law enforcement, and language support. Without a robust tourism logistics framework, Uzbekistan cannot entirely capitalize on its tourism assets. This restricts both the sector's economic potential and the nation's competitiveness in the global tourism industry. Consequently, it is essential to enhance collaboration between public and private sectors, adopt modern technologies, and create a logistics infrastructure that considers the distinct attributes and capabilities of every region. The future of tourism in Uzbekistan relies on the efficiency and sustainability of the planning and management of these logistical systems.

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